

Nitration of *p*-Chlorotoluene and *p*-Chloroisopropylbenzene

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The nitrations of *p*-chlorotoluene and *p*-chloroisopropylbenzene with nitric acid in acetic anhydride have been studied. The product composition from the nitration of *p*-chlorotoluene in acetic anhydride when examined along with the previously known product compositions obtained from the nitrations of *p*-chlorotoluene in varying percentages of sulphuric acid gave information of the degree of attack by the nitronium ion at various positions in *p*-chlorotoluene. The relative rates of nitrations at various nuclear positions for chlorobenzene could then be calculated. Results from nitration of *p*-chloroisopropylbenzene were found to be in agreement with these values.

AN elegant study¹ of the nitration of some halogen substituted benzenes appeared in 1976. The nitration could not be carried out at less than 63% H₂SO₄ because of very slow reactions. It was concluded that the W_i^{Cl} formed returns back to the encounter pair or to the starting material at lower acidities and 1,2-intramolecular migration of the nitro group from the W_i^{Cl} takes place at higher acidities. *ipso*-Substitution and capture of W_i^{Cl} by water were ruled out under the conditions employed^{2,3}. Nitration of *p*-chloroisopropylbenzene with nitric acid in varying concentrations of H₂SO₄ has been studied⁴. A situation similar to the nitration of *p*-chlorotoluene¹ is observed. The proportions of attack of nitronium ion at various positions were determined. The extent of attack at C-Cl could not be calculated and the yield of 2-nitro-4-isopropylchlorobenzene could not be dissected into direct attack and formation by rearrangement of W_i^{Cl} .

The main aim of this study is to determine the proportions of attack by nitronium ion at the *ipso*-, *ortho*-, *meta*- and *para*-positions in chlorobenzene. This is not possible from the results of nitrations of chlorobenzene^{5,6} itself because of the low extent of formation of W_i^{Cl} . Nitrations of chlorine-substituted alkylbenzenes with nitric acid in acetic anhydride is likely to give an answer to this problem as the reaction conditions appropriate with the reaction rate can be achieved and because acetic anhydride is considered to be a very good medium for nucleophilic capture⁷. Two of the chlorine-substituted alkylbenzenes selected for this purpose are *p*-chlorotoluene and *p*-chloroisopropylbenzene. This is because the properties of W_i^{Me} and W_i^{1Pr} have been already evaluated completely^{4,8}.

Experimental

p-Chlorotoluene (technical grade) was twice-distilled (b.p. 106° at 14 mm/Hg) and its purity

checked on the glc before its nitrations. *p*-Chloroisopropylbenzene was prepared from 4-isopropylaniline by diazotisation followed by Sandmeyer reaction⁴; its purity checked on the glc. Anhydrous nitric acid was prepared by distillation of a mixture of 1 part fuming nitric acid and 2 parts of concentrated sulphuric acid at room temperature and pressure ca. 1 mm/Hg in an all-glass apparatus. The colourless distillate was stored in a cold trap and stored in dark cold. Acetic anhydride and urea were of AnalaR grade.

Nitration procedure and working-up of products: The aromatic substrate ($[ArH] \approx 1 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³) and urea ($[Urea] \approx 3 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³) were dissolved in acetic anhydride (5 ml) in a 25 ml conical flask fitted with stirrer (magnetic) and dropping funnel. The conical flask was surrounded by an ice-salt bath and after a few minutes when the temperature of the solution was ca. 0°, a chilled mixture (5 ml) of anhydrous nitric acid in acetic anhydride ($[HNO_3] \approx 1 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³) was added dropwise to the stirred solution over 1 h and the mixture stirred for a further 2 h. The temperature remained at 0–5° in all the reactions. The reactions were quenched by pouring the reaction mixtures into ice-water (~200 ml). A known amount of reference standard was added at this stage. The concentration of the reference standard was ca. 5×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³ as compared to ca. 1×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ of the aromatic substrate. The product was extracted from ether. The ether extracts were washed at least three times with water and dried by using anhydrous magnesium sulphate. The ether was removed under reduced pressure till a concentrated solution (~5 ml) of the products in ether was obtained. This concentrated solution of the products was analysed⁹ using the gas liquid chromatography.

Results and Discussion

Only two products could be detected from the nitration of *p*-chlorotoluene with nitric acid in

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acetic anhydride: 4-chloro-2-nitrotoluene and 4-chloro-3-nitrotoluene. The identities of the products were established by comparing the retention times with known samples under identical conditions. A small amount of the starting material remained unreacted and this was taken into account while calculating the yields of the products. The glc runs were carried out from the ether or chloroform extracts of the products of the reactions after and without washing them with dilute alkali solutions. Yields of the products are 4-chloro-2-nitrotoluene, 9.1% and 4-chloro-3-nitrotoluene (12.0%).

Only three products could be detected from the nitration of *p*-chloroisopropylbenzene: 4-chloro-nitrobenzene (20.2%), 4-chloro-3-nitroisopropylbenzene (10.4%) and 4-chloro-2-nitroisopropylbenzene (52.0%).

The product composition from the nitration of *p*-chlorotoluene in acetic anhydride as obtained during the present work when coupled with the results of nitration of *p*-chlorotoluene in varying percentages of sulphuric acid¹ gives interesting informations and evidence for nucleophilic capture of W_i^{Cl} . Acetic anhydride and 54% H_2SO_4 are considered to be very good media for nucleophilic capture. Thus the yield of 4-chloro-2-nitrotoluene varies from 9.1% in Ac_2O (or 54% H_2SO_4) to ca. 65% in 79.2% H_2SO_4 . The yield of 4-chloro-3-nitrotoluene varies from 12.0% in Ac_2O (or 54% H_2SO_4) to 35.3% in 85% H_2SO_4 . The loss in the yields of products can, therefore, be described in terms of the formation of W_i^{Me} and W_i^{Cl} respectively followed by 1,2-intramolecular migration of nitro group at higher acidities and formation of phenolic products by capture of water at lower acidities.

On this basis the relative rates (%) of substitution at various nuclear positions for the nitration of *p*-chlorotoluene can be determined and are 9.0 ($2f_o$), 12 ($2f_m$), 22.0 (f_p , C-Cl), 57.0 (f_i). Using the values of the relative rates (%) of substitution at various nuclear positions for the nitration of toluene¹⁰ and applying Holleman's product rule¹¹, similar values for chlorobenzene may be evaluated. The relative rates (%) of nitrations at various nuclear positions for chlorobenzene thus obtained are 46.4 ($2f_o$), 1.8 ($2f_m$), 50.1 (f_p), 1.7 (f_i). The values for *ortho*-, *meta*- and *para*-positions are in very good agreement with those reported earlier^{5,6}. The value for *ipso*-position is the result of the present studies only.

Yields of products for nitrations of *p*-chloroisopropylbenzene in 60.2–75.1% sulphuric acid⁴ and in acetic anhydride give a similar picture of W_i^{Cl} as in case of *p*-chlorotoluene. The only fate

of W_i^{i-Pr} , as concluded earlier⁴, is the removal of isopropyl cation to form the nitro-de-isopropylated product, viz. 4-chloronitrobenzene. That the yield of 3-nitro-4-chloroisopropylbenzene remains almost uniformly constant in acetic anhydride and in 60.2–75.1% H_2SO_4 is an evidence of it. It shows that the nitro group is not migrated to an *ortho*-position from the W_i^{i-Pr} under any of the conditions studied. The yield of 2-nitro-4-chloroisopropylbenzene is 52.0% in acetic anhydride, 64.7% in 60.2% H_2SO_4 and then gradually increases upto 71.8% in 75.1% H_2SO_4 . As with *p*-chlorotoluene, this should be related to the partitioning of 1,2-intramolecular migration of the nitro group from the W_i^{Cl} at higher acidities and the capture of water by the W_i^{Cl} to form phenolic products at lower acidities. The degree of attack at C-Cl in 4-chloroisopropylbenzene will, therefore, be ca. 18%. Thus relative rates (%) of nitration at various nuclear positions in 4-chloroisopropylbenzene are known and are 10.4 ($2f_o$), 52.0 ($2f_m$), 18.0 (f_p , C-Cl), 20.0 (f_i). These values are in very good agreement with those found by using such values for isopropylbenzene⁴ and chlorobenzene (see above) and applying Holleman's product rule¹¹. The results from nitration of 4-chloroisopropylbenzene thus afford a good proof for the above found values of f_o , f_m , f_p and f_i for the nitration of chlorobenzene.

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